

Impact of stress and socialization on students' sleeping quality during the lockdown in France

Juliette Bellengier ¹, mélusine blondel ², yunus emre celik ³, kaoutar lanjri ³, Carla Tous Mayol ¹

¹ Track Life Sciences, AIRE master program, Université de Paris, Center for Research and Interdisciplinarity (CRI), F-75004 Paris, France

² Track Learning Sciences, AIRE master program, Université de Paris, Center for Research and Interdisciplinarity (CRI), F-75004 Paris, France

³ Track Digital Sciences, AIRE master program, Université de Paris, Center for Research and Interdisciplinarity (CRI), F-75004 Paris, France

Abstract

The sanitary situation due to the COVID-19 impacted the everyday life of populations at a worldwide scale. Here we focus on students following the French education system and their daily habits during the months of November and December - the second confinement. The increase of exposure to screens, low social interaction, and physical inactivity are known to impact sleeping quality. We explored their effects on students' sleeping quality during this exceptional period with 4 surveys conducted on a sample of 18 students in higher education. Our sample was composed of 12 female and 6 male participants over 18 years old. Our data analysis supports that sleeping quality is negatively affected by stress, but positively and strongly correlated with socialization. Surprisingly, our data analysis does not support a correlation between screen time and sleeping quality. This project could further be disseminated at a bigger scale in France and abroad, thus becoming an international project that could have an impact on better understanding how students' lifestyle and sleep have been affected over the lockdowns.

Keywords: Sleep quality, lockdown, student lifestyle, COVID-19, open science

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Introduction

In March 2020, while facing the COVID-19 pandemic, France's government decided to introduce a lockdown at the national level following Italy's path. All the children, non-medical students as well as the vast majority of the population were told to stay home except for essential needs from March 17th to May 11th. Since then, all the french population and more than half of humanity (*Euronews*, 2020/04/02) have been experiencing lockdowns and we are still exploring their impact on public health.

During the first lockdown in Italy, studies have shown that sleeping quality has been badly affected (Cellini et al, 2020). We already know that sleeping habits and disorders have a big impact on health and could lead to problems such as obesity or hypertension (St-Onge et al, 2016). Sleeping quality has also an impact on memory and learning skills, directly impacting students (Gaultney, 2010). "*Sleep promotes the consolidation of declarative as well as procedural and emotional memories in a wide variety of tasks*" (Diekelmann & Born, 2010). While insufficient sleep is very common among students (Lund et al, 2010), students at risk due to sleeping disorders seem to be more likely to academic failure (Gaultney, 2010). Therefore, sleeping disturbance caused by lockdown lifestyle, could lead to weaker academic performance among students. Given the sanitary situation and its future perspectives, countries around the world will probably experience similar situations in the future, and being able to determine what are the main factors of a decreasing sleeping quality could help figuring out how to avoid such a negative effect

During these confinements, several studies have shown an alteration of sleeping quality and circadian rhythm. Cellini and colleagues (Cellini et al, 2020) showed that during the first wave of the pandemia, participants of their study spent more time in bed but had a lower sleeping quality, found correlation with data usage, especially for young adults who *make extensive use of social media devices that interact with daily activities, including sleep*, and that depression and anxiety were key causes of bad sleeping quality.

The previous research focused on a very precise moment: the first wave and first lockdown and with very restrictive measures (even if they weren't exactly the same in all countries). Since then, countries created intermediate measures to avoid a leap of the pandemic while keeping the economy alive and maintaining certain individual rights. Some rules were eased during the second wave of confinement (schools and companies' offices opened, more stores allowed to remain open,...) and other measures were less restrictive. On October 30th 2020, the French government announced a new lockdown - which was still applying while we were preparing this study. November 25th, Emmanuel Macron announced a prolongation of the lockdown until December 15th. After this date, the lockdown was replaced by a curfew. This lockdown was very different from the first one: more citizens were allowed to go to work, and the rules were not obeyed as much (*La Dépêche*, 2020/11/12) as during the first one. Six month after the first lockdown, **how do these changes of rules and context still have an impact on lifestyle and, more specifically, sleeping quality?**

Whatever the rules, lockdowns and curfew due to the pandemic, all have in common the impact caused in students' lifestyle by reducing their time outside, physical activity, social interactions and increasing their screen usage time. Our hypothesis is that **these factors, separately or combined, have an impact on sleeping quality**. If so, we expect to find a correlation between sleeping quality and these factors. Criterias such as time of sleep and time spent in bed before falling asleep for sleeping quality; or number of people seen in the week, for social interaction, could be relevant data in order to evaluate and test our hypothesis. Studying these data amongst students enables us to have a better understanding of students' sleeping quality during lockdown.

To test this hypothesis, we decided to create a replicable survey with open results so it can lead to further research on students across the world in similar contexts. Due to the situation and time constraints, we started our study during lockdown and before even knowing how the situation and the rules would evolve during the course of this project. Therefore, we decided to focus on the restrictions required by the situation and on their concrete applications in our participants' lives in order to create a survey who could fit different possible situations - i.e., the number of people seen during the week was a clear indicator of the impact of the lockdown or curfew.

Methods

1. Data Collection

The data gathering consisted of several surveys sent to participants with student status, currently studying at an university level (bachelor, master or PhD). A first and introductory survey divide it in three parts: (1) questions to collect general information about the participant (age group, level of education, gender, etc.), (2) their situation during the lockdown (living alone or not, average time spent outside, studying/working from home or not, etc.) and, (3) their sleeping habits based on 5 questions on a weekly basis (hour in which they go to bed and wake up, amount of time to fall asleep, etc.). A total of 54 participants answered this first survey (see link in Table below).

18 participants (33.33%) of participants agreed to continue with three weekly surveys that were sent in order to collect data corresponding only to their sleeping habits section of the introductory survey. 29 participants answered the first weekly survey, 20 in the second and 27 in the third and final one.

As one of the analyses we wanted to perform was studying the temporal evolution of sleeping quality of each participant, we only took into account the students participating in all four surveys for this part of the analysis. We kept all students' participation to study the correlation between our parameters.

The data were anonymized by attributing an ID to each student.

Links to all the surveys and the responses received by the participants can be accessed in the following table (table 1).

Table 1. Links to the different surveys and the anonymized responses. If the direct link does not work, access by copy and pasting the URL provided.

Surveys	Links
Introductory survey	Original empty survey - https://forms.gle/7xKJMEQ341RFPyCo9 Responses - https://tinyurl.com/y3bytbqj
Weekly survey 1	Original empty survey - https://forms.gle/ZJ2j3yUKrrTko51S8 Responses - https://tinyurl.com/y49tvuys
Weekly survey 2	Original empty survey - https://forms.gle/2oDnkV8nSPP6VeHRA Responses - https://tinyurl.com/y55tlmtl
Weekly survey 3	Original empty survey - https://forms.gle/GRsZgUfQuWqCxrUy8 Responses - https://tinyurl.com/y22rbeln

2. Data Analysis

We created a score based on the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), a questionnaire filled by the patient that assesses **sleeping quality** by giving a score from 0 (good) to 3 (bad), to each of the "Sleeping habits" criteria (see Table 2).

Table 2. Sleeping quality score used in this study based on the PSQI.
H: hours, avg: average, num: number.

Score	H of sleep (wake up - go to bed time)	Avg time to fall asleep	Avg num of wakes per night
0	More than 7 hours	Less than 15 minutes	0-1 time
1	6 to 7 hours	16 - 30 minutes	2 times
2	5 to 6 hours	31 to 60 minutes	3 times
3	Less than 5 hours	More than 60 minutes	More than 4 times

As we conducted several surveys, our goal was to be as concise and clear as possible while having a quite low number of weekly questions. Thus, we selected the parameters and questions that we thought were the most important from the PSQI.

It is important to remark that the surveys of this project were weekly based, whereas the PSQI are monthly based. This choice was made based on the changing, unstable and unpredictable situation of COVID-19 in France: the rules were likely to change more often than monthly, especially right before Christmas holidays. In addition, by asking these questions more often and more than once, it was expected to obtain more precise and accurate answers representing the whole period of interest.

Other parameters were of our interest for their potential impact and correlation with sleeping quality, these were screen usage time and socialization. While the screen usage time was directly asked to the participants in the surveys, several questions corresponded to the socialization parameter. Therefore, a socialization score was created, based on binary notation of 3 factors to characterize socialization from 0 (lowest) to 3 (highest) (table 3).

Table 3. Socialization score used in this study.

Score	Live alone	Have a pet	Meet friends
0	Yes (0)	No (0)	No or once a week (0)
1	Yes (0)	No (0)	Yes, twice a week or more (1)

	Yes (0)	Yes (1)	No or once a week (0)
	No (1)	No (0)	No or once a week (0)
2	Yes (0)	Yes (1)	Yes, twice a week or more (1)
	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	No or once a week (0)
	Yes (1)	No (0)	Yes, twice a week or more (1)
3	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	Yes, twice a week or more (1)

Results

1. Participants' general profiles

The data analyzed corresponds to the eighteen participants that answered to the introductory and the weekly surveys.

Overall the characteristics and distribution of the participants in this project are 67% females and 33% males (figure 1, A), 61% of are master students, 22% bachelor students and 16.7% PhD students (figure 1, B). The 90% of them are between 18 and 27 years old (figure 1, C).

And finally, being all the participants take under consideration students in the french educational system, 72% of them are from CRI, whereas the rest are not (figure 1, D).

2. Sleeping quality and its correlation with all factors

The analysis of the correlation between all the parameters (figure 2) helped us determine in which direction look for more information and how to explore the collected data. We find that there is a strong negative correlation between screen time and stress level. As well as it can be observed between sleeping quality and socialization factor.

Figure 2. Correlation heat map.

3. Sleeping quality and screen time

The first parameter studied is the screen time. We expected to see a strong correlation between the time spent in front of screens and the sleeping quality of students, especially in lockdown conditions where students have to spend more time in front of computers to follow online courses. Interestingly, we did not observe any correlation between sleeping quality and screen time (figure 3, A). This could be explained by the fact that the students had to estimate the screen time by themselves (with the help of their phone's statistics). These numbers could be

over or underestimated. Moreover, it should be considered that it might be possible that not all screen time has the same impact on sleeping quality: it could depend on the use that is being made, the time of use (for instance in bed before going to sleep) or the device used. We would need a deeper and more detailed study to find this out.

4. Sleeping quality and stress

We also studied the correlation between the stress level of students and the sleeping quality. (figure 3, B). A strong correlation was observed: the higher the stress level, the higher the average score of sleeping, and so the worst the sleeping quality (0 corresponding to the best score in terms of quality of sleep). However, the variability of the data is really high as indicated by the blue and purple areas on the plots, probably due to our small sample size ($n < 20$). Additionally, we also noted some points were really scattered and/or did not match the fitting curve. Thus, our results have to be taken with precaution.

Figure 3. (a) Scattered plot of the sleeping quality in function of screen time.
(b) Scattered plot of the sleeping quality in function of the stress level.

5. Sleeping quality and socialization

As mentioned in the methods section, the level of socialization of the participants was studied taking into account several aspects, such as time spent with other people or living alone (figure 4, A and B).

Figure 4. (a) Scattered plot of the sleeping quality in function of the time spent with friends, and (b) if the participant is living alone or not (0 or 1).

We noticed a strong correlation between sleeping quality and the 'meeting friends' factor: from our results the sleep score decreases when meeting friends time increases. Meaning that participants that socialize with friends tend to have better sleeping quality.

However, from our data it does not seem that sleeping quality is correlated with living alone.

To further investigate the previous results, we developed a socialization index.

It combined three factors: (1) living alone or not, (2) having a pet or not and (3) the number of time spent with friends. Interestingly, we observed a negative correlation between these two factors (figure 8). Suggesting that the higher the socialization score, the lower the sleeping one (associated to a good sleep quality). To conclude, we found that on the studied sample, the higher the socialization score, the better is the sleep quality.

Figure 5. Scattered plot of the sleeping quality in function of the socialization factor

Discussion

Based on the size of our sample, further research needs to be done to confirm or infirm our results. We decided to especially focus on three measurements that appeared to be the most relevant because of previous research and because of the correlation found within our data: screen time, stress level and socialization.

Our data (figure 3, A) do not indicate any correlation between the sleeping quality of the students and their screen time, which is very surprising because recent studies have shown some correlation during lockdown (Cellini et al, 2020) and in other contexts. Nevertheless, because of the low amount of participants, it is possible that such a correlation doesn't appear because of a lack of data.

As exposed in our results (figure 3, B), the stress level of the students was correlated with their sleeping quality. This result could be explained by the fact that a high level of stress might worsen sleeping quality. Yet, the opposite could also be true: if the students have a low sleeping quality they could be more likely to have a high level of stress.

Finally, according to our data analysis (figure 5) it seems that there is a strong correlation between sleeping quality and socialization. However, these results need to be taken with precaution regarding several biases of the study: non-randomized trial conducted on a really small sample of students. When comparing socialization parameters separately, the correlation was stronger between sleeping quality and the meeting friends factors. These data indicate that socialization could be one important factor to improve sleeping quality, especially through quality time with the close ones. This result is not surprising because some evidence (Altena et al, 2020) in that direction was shown before.

To sum up, our results indicate that two factors have a significant relation with sleeping quality. While the stress level could worsen it, socialization could improve it. We did not find any correlation between sleeping quality and screen time but we believe that further research should be made in that direction.

Research's bias

Due to certain inevitable bias, consequences of the context of the experiment, our results should be considered as preliminary results. Our sample size being very small (the number of participants was inferior to 20, compared to the whole French population of 67 millions), this has a strong influence on the significance of our results. Moreover, our survey was disseminated mainly between CRI students or other students recruited using our networks. Our sample was not randomized, therefore, it is not possible to state that the studied sample is representative of the whole studied population (students enrolled in a French degree living in France). The low participation, together with selection bias and self-declaration bias, which also might lead to approximative results (e.g possibility to forget, uncertain accuracy...) should incite our readers to be cautious with our data, results and analysis presented.

Speculation

In order to go deeper with our data, further research could be made. Firstly, the correlation between screen time and sleeping quality that did not appear in our research was present in previous research. It might be interesting to look into that by studying more precisely the time of the day when the screen is used, especially before sleep. Besides the use of media was analyzed and showed an impact on sleeping quality in previous research (Léger et al, 2020) but we could suppose that students mainly read and watch news on screens (phone, computer or TV). Analyzing both screen time and use of media (how often, before sleep or not) could be relevant to distinguish them and see which one has the biggest effect on sleep.

More complete studies could also be run to better understand the relationship between stress and sleeping quality: which factor impacts the other one? This knowledge could help to elaborate more efficient recommendations for students and universities.

Socialization factors could also be analyzed more deeply. According to our results, meeting friends is the most effective way to prevent bad sleep and, more globally, not being alone seems to help. It would be interesting to find out which (face-to-face and on-distance) practices are the most efficient to see how to choose wisely the few interactions that we can have during a lockdown.

At last, with more participants we could see the impact of gender because during previous studies men and women did not show similar results in sleeping quality (Altena et al, 2020). In order to involve more participants, the study could be shared with students from other universities through social media and through a call for participation relayed by the universities. It would enable us to have a more diverse sample: students from all parts of France, students from different backgrounds, studying in different fields and universities.

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